

The Influence of Brand Image & Experiential Marketing to Consumer Satisfaction & Loyalty Café in Surabaya

Author Details:

Antonius Jan Wellyantony Putro

School of Business, Widya Mandala Catholic University -42, Dinoyo, Surabaya, Indonesia

Tel : 62 81 750 22522 Email : janwellyan@gmail.com

Abstrak— Currently the cafe business competition is very tight, to be able to maintain customer loyalty, café entrepreneurs must be able to create customer satisfaction. One strategy to create customer satisfaction is to emphasize more on Brand Image and Experiential marketing variables as the basis for the marketing strategy. *This research designed for survey method of the 150 respondents, with non-probability samplings technique. Respondents were taken from Surabaya Indonesian. Meanwhile, SEM was used to analyze the model. The result of this research indicated that there is a positive influence between Brand Images, Experiential Marketing, and Customer Satisfaction to Customer Loyalty.*

Kata Kunci— Cafe, Brand Images, Experiential Marketing, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this era, consumers prefer cafes that have their own uniqueness and characteristics that are very different from other cafes. In addition to luring consumers to be loyal to the cafe, cafe owners must also have and implement strategies to compete with their competitors, one of the strategies that cafe owners need to do is to create Customer Satisfaction, by innovating in terms of products, services, and the concept of interior design to win the competition, this is in line with what was expressed by (Tjiptono, 2014: 353) that customer satisfaction is an emotional response of a person due to experiences related to certain products or services purchased, or behavior patterns such as current behavior. shopping and buyer behavior.

Based on previous research concluded that customer satisfaction has a significant effect on customer loyalty (Wu and Tseng, 2015). One way to build Customer Satisfaction is by paying attention to brand image and experiential marketing. Because according to Zena and Hadisumarto (2012: 108) experiential marketing is a marketing approach that provides an extraordinary framework

for combining elements between experience (experience) and entertainment (entertainment) into a product or service. Experiential Marketing aims to provide a unique experience for customers through sense, feel, think, act, and relate. Meanwhile, brand image is a part of a brand that is easily recognizable such as symbols, colors, letter shapes, and consumer perceptions (Ferrinadewi, 2008; in Putri, et al., 2016). Therefore, researchers want to find out more about how brand image, experiential marketing and customer satisfaction can affect customer loyalty at a cafe.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Brand Image

Sutopo (2017) brand image is a person's perception of a brand which is reflected in the brand association in consumer memory. Mohajerani and Miremadi (2012) explain that a brand will give an overall impression that is made in the public's mind about something. If someone has an unforgettable impression, then this will make someone always remember the brand in the memory of consumers.

Meanwhile, the research indicators measuring the variable brand image cafe according to Jin et al., (2012) are:

- This cafe brand has a fashionable and trendy image
- This cafe brand has a reputation for quality
- This cafe brand is well known.

2. Experiential Marketing

Indrawati and Fatharani (2016) state that Experiential marketing intends to create unique experiences for customers and increase their purchase intention through senses, taste, thought, action, and connecting. Meanwhile, according to Maghnati et al., (2012) said that Experiential Marketing not only increases customer emotion and taste stimulation but does not neglect the quality and function of its products and services.

Experiential marketing also provides experiences that provide sensory, emotional, cognitive, behavioral, and relational values that

replace functional values (Schmitt, 1999: 22; in Khasanah, 2015). The following are indicators used in measuring experiential marketing variables according to Nigam (2012): Sense, Feel, Think, Act, and Relate.

3. Customer Satisfaction.

According to Howard and Sheth (in Tjiptono, 2014: 353), it explains that customer satisfaction is an emotional response to experiences related to certain products or services purchased or even behavior patterns (such as shopping behavior and buyer behavior). The word satisfaction comes from the Latin word "satis" which means (good enough, adequate) and "facio" which means (doing or making), so it can be concluded that satisfaction can be interpreted as "an effort to fulfill something" (Tjiptono and Chandra, 2016). If the product or service exceeds the desired expectations, consumers will feel happy and are said to be satisfied with the goods or services used (Kotler and Keller, 2012: 13). Meanwhile, if the services provided are of low quality, do not reach customer expectations, this will cause consumer dissatisfaction (Bagram and Khan, 2012).

The following are the indicators used in measuring the universal customer satisfaction variables according to Dutka (2008, in Logiawan and Subagio, 2014):

- a. Attributes related to product
- b. Attributes related to service
- c. Attributes related to purchase

4. Customer Loyalty

According to Jones and Sasser (1995, in Marlien, 2017) Customer loyalty is an endogenous variable caused by a combination of satisfaction, so customer loyalty is a function of satisfaction. Loyalty in service marketing is defined as a response that is closely related to an agreement to uphold the commitment that underlies the continuity of the relationship (Tjiptono, 2014: 392).

Consumers are not measured by how much they make purchases, but how often they make repeated purchases, including recommending others to buy (Kotler, 2012). In forming loyalty, there are several indicators of strong loyalty according to Chen and Liu (2017), namely:

- a. Recent purchase activities
- b. Repurchase Intention
- c. Recommendation intention

5. Hypothesis Development

5.1 Effect of Brand Image on Customer Satisfaction

According to (Pramudyo, 2012; in Herliza and Saputri, 2016) brands have a role in marketing an organization, this is because they have the potential to influence consumer perceptions and expectations regarding the goods or services offered which in turn can affect customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, according to Lodhi (2013), brand image and customer satisfaction have a relationship between brand image and customer satisfaction by seeing people's reactions to different salespeople.

A high level of satisfaction is formed when brands meet customer needs far more than competing brands (Hafeez et al., 2010). Research conducted by Neupane (2015) shows that brand image has a positive and significant relationship with customer satisfaction.

H1: Brand Image has a positive effect on Customer Satisfaction at Cafe visitors in Surabaya.

5.2 Effect of Experiential Marketing on Customer Satisfaction

According to research Utarsih (2016) states that consumers always want a product whose presence can provide an experience. This is in accordance with the opinion of Scmitt (1999, in Wu and Tseng, 2015) which states that the dimensions of experiential marketing, namely sense, feel, think, act, and relate are often used by marketers to increase customer satisfaction. According to Wu and Tseng (2015), experiential marketing is positively related to customer satisfaction.

H2: Experiential Marketing has a positive effect on Customer Satisfaction at Cafe visitors in Surabaya.

5.3 The Influence of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty

A high level of pleasure or satisfaction will create an emotional bond with a certain brand, and this creates high customer loyalty (Kotler et al., 2000; in Lopumeten and Tomaso, 2018). This is in accordance with the opinion according to Kotler et al., (2012) that satisfied customers will feel loyal, customers will make repeated purchases and are willing to recommend to others. In research according to (Hafeez, 2012) explains that consumer satisfaction can increase customer loyalty. This is supported by research according to Manurung (2009; in Hijjah, 2015) which states that there is a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

H3: Customer Satisfaction has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty among visitors to Cafe in Surabaya.

5.4. The Influence of Brand Image on Customer Loyalty

One of the factors that can affect brand loyalty is brand image (Annisa and Utama, 2016). According to (Chandra, 2005; in Sutopo, 2017) says that a strong brand image can provide a number of advantages, one of which is customer loyalty and greater repurchase. Loyalty can be translated into the willingness of customers to pay higher prices, often 20% to 25% higher than competing brands (Kotler and Keller, 2012; in Sutopo, 2017).

Based on the results of previous research conducted by Chao (2015), it shows that brand image has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. Researchers conclude that it is important to pay attention to brand image to give a positive impression to consumers.

H4: Brand Image has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty to Cafe visitors in Surabaya.

5.5. The Influence of Experiential Marketing on Customer Loyalty

Experiential marketing can increase customer loyalty, for example by making repeated purchases. Improving one's experience during the buying process can help to maintain consumer loyalty (Alkilani et al., 2013; in Chao, 2015), which can then affect customer loyalty (Lee and Chang, 2012; in Chao, 2015).

Based on Wu and Tseng's (2015) research, it shows that experiential marketing has a significant effect on customer loyalty.

H5: Experiential Marketing has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty among visitors to Cafe in Surabaya.

5.6. The Influence of Brand Image on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction

Image is a valuable intangible asset of a company (Hidajahningtas, et al., 2013). A good image will increase customer satisfaction, service quality, loyalty, and repurchase intention (Bloemer et al., 1998; Da Silva et al., 2008 and Lai et al., 2009). It can be concluded that the brand image in a cafe will make consumers feel satisfied so that satisfied consumers will lead to a loyal attitude towards the cafe.

H6: Brand Image has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction with Cafe visitors in Surabaya.

5.7 Effect of Experiential Marketing on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction

Experiential marketing is very useful for a company that wants to increase its existing brand at the decline stage, as a product differentiator from competing products, create an image and identity of a company, and increase innovation and get customers to want to try and buy the product (Maghnati et al., 2012). In this modern era, companies are no longer just offering products or services, but they also need to create a consumer experience which is the ultimate goal of creating an interesting experience for consumers (Chao, 2015).

According to previous research, it also explains that experiential marketing is able to promote increased customer satisfaction (Tsaour, 2007; Lee, Hsiao and Yang, 2011; Alkilani, Ling and Abzakh, 2013), which further affects customer loyalty (Lee and Chang, 2012).

H7: Experiential marketing has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction with visitors to Cafe in Surabaya.

III. METHODOLOGY

This causal study the effect of Brand Images, Experiential Marketing and Customer Satisfaction on Consumer Loyalty, which is conducted in the form of a survey. Explanatory research is applied to explain the relationship between variables, both direct relationships and mediation relationships. Model Structure Analysis and Research Hypotheses are proven by SEM, on LISREL. The research population is Surabaya - Indonesian citizens who have been to a certain cafe in Surabaya at least 3 times in a row within the last 1 month. The Non-Probability Sampling technique was chosen, in order to obtain respondents in accordance with the research construct. Purposive Sampling, applied to get the best respondents This data was obtained through a questionnaire that was distributed and filled out by 150 respondents.

IV. RESULT & ANALYSIS

The multivariate normality test resulted in a p-value = 0.000, below a significant alpha of 5% or 0.05, so it can be said that the data used in this study were not normally distributed. Based on the Validation Test, all indicators are declared valid,

because the loading factor value obtained by each indicator is greater than 1.96.

For Structural Model fit test :

CS = 0.54*BI + 0.43*EM, Errorvar.= 0.096 , R² = 0.90

(0.21) (0.18) (0.037)
2.63 2.32 2.57

CL = 0.51*CS + 0.27*BI + 0.23*EM, Errorvar.= 0.029 , R² = 0.97

(0.15) (0.14) (0.100) (0.014)
3.38 2.01 2.30 2.12

Results of the Hypothesis Test:

Tabel 1
Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis	Relation	Estimate	T-Value	Cut Off	Ref
H1	BI → CS	0,54	2,63	>1,96	significant
H2	EM → CS	0,43	2,32	>1,96	Significant
H3	CS → CL	0,51	3,38	>1,96	Significant
H4	BI → CL	0,27	2,01	>1,96	Significant
H5	EM → CL	0,23	2,30	>1,96	significant
H6	BI → CS → CL	0,27	1,81	>1,96	Not Significant
H7	EM → CS → CL	0,23	2,38	>1,96	Significant

Source : Processed SEM

The statistical analysis of the hypothesis of the effect of brand image on customer satisfaction shows that the t-value has a value of 2.63, which is greater than t table = 1.96 with an estimated value of 0.54 which indicates that the higher the brand image, the more likely it is to increase customer satisfaction. So that the test results prove that "brand image has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at cafes in Surabaya". The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Neupane (2015) which shows that brand image has a positive and significant relationship with customer satisfaction.

Overall experiential marketing is a unique experience for customers who can increase their purchase intention through senses, taste, thought, action, and relationship. The statistical analysis of the hypothesis of the effect of experiential marketing on customer satisfaction shows that the t-value has a value of 2.32, which is greater than t table = 1.96 with an estimated value of 0.43 which indicates that the higher the experiential marketing, the more likely it is to increase customer

satisfaction. So that the test results prove "experiential marketing has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the Cafe in Surabaya". The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Scmitt (1999, in Wu and Tseng, 2015)

The statistical analysis of the hypothesis of the effect of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty shows that the t-value has a value of 3.38, which is greater than t table = 1.96 with an estimated value of 0.51 which indicates that the higher the customer satisfaction, the more likely it is to increase customer loyalty. So that the test results prove "customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty at a cafe in Surabaya". The results of this study are supported by Kotler et al., (2012) that satisfied customers will feel loyal, customers will make repeat purchases and will recommend to others.

The statistical analysis of the hypothesis of the effect of brand image on customer loyalty shows that the t-value has a value of 2.01, which is greater than t table = 1.96 with an estimated value of 0.27 which indicates that the higher the brand image, the more likely it is to increase customer loyalty. So that the test results prove "brand image has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty at cafes in Surabaya". Consumers will feel satisfied if the product given exceeds the imagined expectations, this is supported by the opinion of Pramudyo (2012, in Herliza, et al., 2016).

The statistical analysis of the hypothesis of the effect of experiential marketing on customer loyalty shows that the t-value has a value of 2.30 which is greater than t table = 1.96 with an estimated value of 0.23 which indicates that the higher the experiential marketing, the more likely it is to increase customer loyalty. So that the test results prove "experiential marketing has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty at a cafe in Surabaya. This is supported by research according to Alkilani et al., (2013; in Chao, 2015) which shows that improving one's experience during the buying process can help to maintain consumer loyalty, which can then affect customer loyalty (Lee and Chang, 2012; in Chao, 2015).

Judging from the results of the hypothesis analysis of the effect of brand image on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction shows that the t-value has a value of 1.81, which is smaller than t table = 1.96 with an estimated value of 0.27. Thus, it can be said that a cafe that has a good brand image does not necessarily make a consumer

immediately interested in behaving well towards the cafe. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Wu, Tai-chi (2015) show that brand image has no significant effect on loyalty.

The statistical analysis of the hypothesis of the effect of brand image on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction shows that the t-value has a value of 2.38 which is greater than t table = 1.96 with an estimated value of 0.22 which indicates that the higher customer satisfaction is caused by high experiential marketing tends to increase customer loyalty. So that the test results prove "experiential marketing has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction at the cafe in Surabaya. The results of this study are supported by past research which confirms that experiential marketing can promote increased customer satisfaction (Tsaur, 2007; Lee, Hsiao and Yang, 2011; Alkilani, Ling and Abzakh, 2013), which in turn affects customer loyalty (Lee and Chang, 2012).

V. RESULT

REFERENSI

- i. Alkilani, K., Ling, K. C. and Abzakh, A. A. (2013). *The impact of experiential marketing and customer satisfaction on customer commitment in the world of social networks. Asian Social Science*, 9(1), 262-270.
- ii. Annisa, M., dan Utama, A. (2016). *The Influence of Brand Image, Brand Trust, and Customer satisfaction Toward Courier Service Brand Loyalty (A Case Study of Indonesian Pos Courier Service Customers of Economic Faculty of Yogyakarta State University). Jurnal Studi Manajemen & Organisasi*.
- iii. Bagram, M.M.M. dan Khan, S. (2012). *Attaining consumer loyalty. The role of consumer attitude and consumer behaviour. International Review of Management and Business Research*. 1 (1), 1-8.
- iv. Chen, C. M., dan Liu, H. M. (2017). *Exploring the Impact of Airlines Service Quality on Customer Loyalty: Evidence from Taiwan. International Journal of Business and Management*. Vol. 12, No. 5
- v. Chao, R. F. (2015). *The Impact of Experimental Marketing on Customer Loyalty for Fitness Clubs: Using Brand Image and Satisfaction as the Mediating Variables. The Journal of International Management Studies*, Vol.10 No.2 52-60.
- vi. Da Silva, R.V. & Alwi, S.F.S. (2008). *Online Corporate Brand Image, Satisfacton, and Loyalty. Journal of Brand Management*, Vol. 16.
- vii. Hafeez, S and Bakhtiar M. (2012). *The Impact of Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and loyalty Programs on Customers Loyalty, Evidence form Banking Sector of Pakistan. International Journal of Business and Social Science*. Vol. 3 No. 16, p. 200- 20.
- viii. Hanif, M., Sehrish, H., dan Adnan, R. (2010). *Factor Affecting Customer Satisfaction. International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, ISSN 1450-2887, Issue 60.
- ix. Herliza, R., dan Saputri, M. E. (2016). *Pengaruh Brand Image terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Studi pada Zara di Mall Pvj Bandung The Influence of Brand Image to Customer Satisfaction a Case Study of Zara At Pvj Mall Bandung Program Studi Administrasi Bisnis Fakultas Komunikasi dan Bisnis. Journal Of Management*, Vol.3(2), 1949–1955.
- x. Hidajahningtyas, Nurullah, Andi Sularso dan Imam Suroso. (2013). *Pengaruh Citra, Kualitas Sakit Daerah Dr. Soebandi Kabupaten Jember. Jurnal Ekonomi Akuntansi dan Manajemen (JEAM)*, Vol. 12. No. 1. Hal. 39 – 53.

- xi. Hijjah, R., & Ardiansari, A. (2015). *Pengaruh Customer Experience Dan Customer Value Terhadap Customer Loyalty Melalui Customer Satisfaction*. *Management Analysis Journal*, Vol.4(4), 281–288.
- xii. Indrawati dan Fatharani, U. S. (2016). *The Effect of Experiential Marketing towards Customer Satisfaction on Online Fashion Store in Indonesia*. *First International Conference on Advanced Business and Social Sciences*, 227-236.
- xiii. Jin, N., Lee, S., dan Huffman, L. (2012). *Impact of Restaurant Experience on Brand Image and Customer Loyalty Moderating Role of Dining Motivation*. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*.
- xiv. Khasanah, I. (2015). *Analisis Pengaruh Nilai Pelanggan, Experiential Marketing dan Rasa Kepercayaan Terhadap Kepuasan pelanggan (Studi Kasus Hotel Pondok Tingal Magelang)*. *Jurnal Studi Manajemen & Organisasi*.
- xv. Kotler, et al 2012. *Marketing Management*, ed 14. Prentice Hall, United State of America.
- xvi. Lai, F., Griffin, M., dan Babin, B. J. (2009). *How Quality, Value, Image, and Satisfaction Create Loyalty at a Chinese Telecom*. *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 62
- xvii. Lee, M. S., Hsiao, H. D. and Yang, M. F. (2011). *The Study of the Relationships among Experiential Marketing, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty*. *The International Journal of Organizational Innovation*, 3(2), 353-379.
- xviii. Lee, T. H., and Chang, Y. S. (2012). *The Influence of Experiential Marketing and Activity Involvement on the Loyalty Intentions of Wine Tourists in Taiwan*. *Leisure Studies*, 31(1), 103-121.
- xix. Lodhi, N. R. (2013). *Effect of Brand Image on Brand Loyalty and Role of Customer Satisfaction in it*. *Comsats Institute Of Information Technology Sahiwal*. Vol.26 (10)
- xx. Logiawan, Y., dan Subagio, H. (2014). *Analisis Customer Value terhadap Customer Loyalty dengan Customer Satisfaction sebagai Variabel Intervening pada Restoran Bandar Djakarta Surabaya*. *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran Petra*, Vol.2 No.1.
- xxi. Lopumeten, R.N., dan Tomaso, S., K. (2018). *Pengaruh Experiential Marketing dan Kepuasan Pelanggan terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan (Studi pada Restoran Imperial Resto di Kota Ambon)*. *Jurnal SOSOQ*, Vol.6(1).
- xxii. Maghnati, F., Ling, K. C., dan Nasermodeli, A. (2012). *Exploring the Relationship between Experiential Marketing and Experiential Value in the Smartphone Industry*. *International Business Research*, Vol.5(11), 169–177.
- xxii. Marlien, R. A., Wahyujati, D. I., Rr, A., dan Sutedja, B. (2014). *Model anteseden loyalitas pelanggan berbasis kualitas layanan*, 679–685.
- xxiii. Mohajerani, P., & Miremadi, A. (2012). *Customer satisfaction modeling in hotel industry: A case study of Kish Island in Iran*. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 4(3), 134-152.
- xxiv. Neupane, R. (2015). *The effects of brand image on customer satisfaction and loyalty intention in retail super market chain*. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management*, 2(1), 9- 26.
- xxv. Nigham, A. (2012). *Modeling Relationship Between Experiential Marketing, Experiential Value and Purchase Intentions in Organized Quick Service Chain restaurants Shoppers Using Structural Equation Modeling Approach*. *Paradigm*, Vol.XVI No.1.
- xxvi. Putri, N.A., Arifin, Z., dan Wilopo. (2016). *Pengaruh Citra Merek, Kepercayaan Merek, dan Switching Barrier terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan dan Dampaknya pada Loyalitas Pelanggan (Survei Pada Mahasiswa S1 Jurusan Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis Fakultas Ilmu Administrasi Universitas Brawijaya Tahun 2014/2015 Pengguna Smartphone Samsung)*. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, Vol.32(1).
- xxv. Sutopo, T., W. (2017). *Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Produk dan Citra Merek terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan melalui Kepuasan pelanggan sebagai Variabel (Studi pada Pelanggan Air Minum Dalam Kemasan Club di Semarang)*. *Diponegoro Journal of Management*, Vol.6(4).
- xxvi. Tjiptono, F. (2014). *Pemasaran Jasa*. Yogyakarta : Andi.
- xxvii. Tjiptono, F., dan Chandra, G. (2016). *Service, Quality dan Satisfaction Edisi 4*. Yogyakarta : Andi.
- xxviii. Tsaor, S. H., Chiu, Y. T. and Wang, C. H. (2007). *The visitors behavioral consequences of experiential marketing: an empirical study on Taipei Zoo*. *Journal of Travel and Tourism Marketing*, 21(1), 47-64.
- xxix. Utarsih, H. 2016. *Pengaruh Experiential Marketing, Customer Relationship Marketing,*

Dan Customer Satisfaction Terhadap Customer Loyalty Hotel Bintang 3 Sampai Dengan 5 Di Kota Bandung. Jurnal indonesia membangun Vol. 3. No. 1. <http://jurnal-inaba.hol.es> Diakses pada tanggal 15 Maret 2018.

- xxx. Wu, M.-Y., dan Tseng, L.-H. (2014). *Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in an Online Shop: An Experiential Marketing Perspective. International Journal of Business and Management, Vol.10(1), 104–115.*
- xxxi. Wu, Tai-Chi. (2015). *The Journal of Business Management. The Influence of Service Quality, Brand Image, and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty for Private Karaoke Rooms in Taiwan. Vol.11 No. 1*
- xxxii. Zena, P. A., dan Hadisumarto, A. D. (2012). *The Study of Realtionship among Experiential Marketing, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty. Asean Marketing Journal, 4(1), 37-46.*